

Unsymmetrical Cyanines Derived from Thiazoles and Thiadiazoles

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Two series of unsymmetrical cyanines are described. The first series is derived from thiadiazole as the fixed basic nucleus and a number of basic nuclei as the variable component. In the second series, 4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole is used as the fixed basic nucleus and two other nuclei as the variable basic component.

The absorption maxima of the above dyes have been determined and from the absorption data, the corresponding deviations have been calculated.

The relationship between deviation and relative basicity has been clearly brought out by considering the energy level diagrams of both symmetrical and unsymmetrical cyanines.

In the present investigation, two series of unsymmetrical cyanines have been prepared. The first series, represented by the general expression given below, is derived from thiadiazole as the fixed basic nucleus and (a) quinoline-2, (b) quinoline-4, (c) benzothiazole, (d) benzoxazole, and (e) α -picoline as the variable basic nuclei.

[Nucleus B=quinoline-2, quinoline-4, benzothiazole, benzoxazole, α -picoline]

The second series having the structure given below is derived from 4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole as the fixed basic nucleus and quinoline-2 and benzothiazole as the variable nuclei.

[Nucleus B=quinoline-2, benzothiazole]

The absorption maxima of the above dyes have been determined and with the help of these data, their deviations calculated. As is well known, deviation is the difference between the absorption maximum of the dye concerned and the mean value of the absorp-

tion maxima of the two corresponding symmetrical cyanines¹. The procedure for calculating deviation is illustrated below by taking the case of the trimethin unsymmetrical dye (I) ($n=0$; nucleus B=quinoline-2) derived from 5-phenylamino-2, 3-dimethyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole. The absorption maximum of the symmetrical cyanine derived from quinoline is $610 \text{ m}\mu$ and that derived from thiadiazole is $542 \text{ m}\mu$. The mean value is therefore $(610+542)/2$, i.e., $576 \text{ m}\mu$. The unsymmetrical dye, however, absorbs at $567 \text{ m}\mu$; the deviation is therefore $9 \text{ m}\mu$.

It is accepted¹ that deviation is a measure of the relative order of basicity of a number of basic nuclei linked through a chromophoric chain to one fixed basic nucleus in a series of unsymmetrical cyanines. The greater the deviation, the greater is the basicity. The relationship between deviation and relative basicity is clearly brought out in an interesting manner, elucidated below, by considering the energy level diagrams of both symmetrical and unsymmetrical cyanines. The present approach has not been reported before.

In the case of a symmetrical cyanine, the two extreme structures possess nearly the same energy and the energy levels of the extreme structures and also of the ground and excited state are shown in Fig. 1. In the case of an unaymmetrical cyanine, the situation is somewhat different. Two possibilities may arise. The two extreme structures may be either of equal energy or they may be of unequal energy. In the former case, the energy levels of the extreme structures and of the ground and excited state would be very much similar to that shown in Fig. 1. In this case, the two nuclei being of the same order of basicity, the resulting dye absorbs at a wave length, say, 'X', the value of which is the arithmetic mean of the absorption maxima of the two related symmetrical cyanines. In the second possibility, which will arise when the two nuclei constituting the dye are of unequal basicity, the two extreme structures 'a' and 'b' do not possess the same energy and as a result of this, there is greater separation between 'g' and 'e' in the energy level diagram in Fig. 2, as compared to that in Fig. 1. Suppose the dye concerned absorbs at a wave length 'Y'. The difference between 'X' and 'Y' (X being the value if the two extreme structures have the same energy as in Fig. 1) gives the deviation.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

If one of the two basic nuclei is fixed and the other basic nucleus is changed, according to the increasing or decreasing basicity of the second basic nucleus, the difference bet-

1. Brooker, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1942, 14, 275; Brooker *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 875; 1951, 73, 5326; Brooker, *Experientia*, Supplementum II-XIVth International Congress of Pure and Applied Chemistry, July, 1955.

ween the energy levels of 'a' and 'b' and consequently of 'g' and 'e' would either increase or decrease. But since the difference between the value of 'X' and 'Y', which is a measure of deviation, is proportional to the distance between 'g' and 'e', the deviation will increase or decrease according as the basicity of the second basic nucleus is either increased or decreased.

The above treatment therefore provides an elucidation of the generalisation that deviation is a measure of relative basicity.

Experimental verification of the relationship between deviation and relative basicity can be had from the data recorded in Tables III, IV, and V. It will be seen that in a series of unsymmetrical cyanines derived from thiadiazole as the fixed basic nucleus and a number of variable basic nuclei like α -picoline, quinoline-4, etc., the respective deviations are 30 $m\mu$ for α -picoline, 11 $m\mu$ for quinoline-4, 9 $m\mu$ for quinoline-2, 7- $m\mu$ for benzothiazole, and 6 $m\mu$ for benzoxazole. The same sequence in the value of deviation is also maintained in case of the corresponding pentamethin cyanines derived from the above basic nuclei. Since increasing deviation indicates increasing order of basicity, the relative order of basicities of the various nuclei used as the second component in the unsymmetrical cyanines derived from thiadiazole conforms to the following order: α -picoline > quinoline-4 > quinoline-2 > benzothiazole > benzoxazole.

The dye preparations are described in the Experimental.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sensitisation.—The sensitisation spectra of some of the dyes have also been determined by the method of Doja *et al.*² with slight modifications in the experimental technique.

The light source was a straight filament lamp of 12 volts 36 watts. The spectrograph used was a constant deviation spectrograph. A wedge placed in front of the slit served the purpose of rotating logarithmic sector used by the above workers.

To record the sensitisation spectra, Ilford N 40 plates were used. The internal scale used was prepared by taking standard lines of mercury, cadmium, and potassium etc.

TABLE A

Code No. of the dye. Photograph number.	Nature of the dye.			Sensitisation.		Abs. max.
	Fixed nucleus.	Variable nucleus		Range.	Maxima.	
1	5-Phenyl- amino-1,3,4, thiadiazole	Benzothiazole	Trimethin	550-690 $m\mu$	600 $m\mu$	544 $m\mu$
2	Do	Quinoline-2	Do	550-690	630	567
3	Do	Do	Pentamethin	600-770	690	662
4	Do	Benzothiazole	Do	580-690	660	640
5	Unsensitised plate	..	..	380-550	460	..

2. *This Journal*, 1941, 18, 281.

It will be seen from the above table that the sensitisation range and sensitisation maxima roughly correspond to absorption maxima. All the dyes studied are good sensitizers in their respective ranges.

The sensitivity of the N 40 plates lies between 380 to 550 m μ as will be seen from photograph No. 5 (Fig. 3).

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolium Iodide.—2,3-Dimethyl-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (3g.) and diphenylformamidine (1.9g.) in acetic anhydride (12 ml) were refluxed for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled and excess of ether was then added. The precipitate obtained on adding ether was collected by decantation. It was washed with acetone and benzene, m. p. 252°, yield 45%. (Found: C, 47.5; H, 4.05. C₁₉H₁₉ON₄IS requires C, 47.69; H, 3.9%).

2-(4-Acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide was prepared by refluxing 2,3-dimethyl-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (3g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.56 g.) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) for 50 minutes. The product was worked up as described above, m.p. 174°, yield 55%. (Found: C, 50.2; H, 4.2. C₂₁H₂₁ON₄IS requires C, 50.0; H, 4.17%).

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-4-p-bromophenyl-3-methylthiazolium Iodide.—4-p-Bromophenyl-2,3-dimethylthiazolium iodide (3.8 g.) and diphenylformamidine (2 g.) in acetic anhydride (12 ml) were refluxed for 20 mins. The resulting compound was worked up as above, m.p. 163°, yield 40%. (Found: C, 44.22; H, 3.6. C₂₀H₁₉ON₂BrIS requires C, 44.3; H, 3.5%).

2-(4-Acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl)-4-p-bromophenyl-3-methylthiazolium Iodide.—4-p-Bromophenyl-2,3-dimethylthiazolium iodide (3.8 g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.5 g.) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) were refluxed for 70 minutes. The product was separated as described before, m.p. 205°, yield 45%. (Found: C, 46.46; H, 3.75. C₂₂H₂₁ON₂BrIS requires C, 46.5; H, 3.69%).

TABLE I

*Unsymmetrical cyanines derived from 5-phenylamino-2,3-dimethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole.**

Dye No.	Nature of nucleus B.	Value of n.	M.P.	λ_{max} .	% Carbon .		%Hydrogen .	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Quinoline-2	1	172°(d)	587m μ	52.68	53.80	4.10	4.20
2	"	2	209°	662	54.60	54.70	4.28	4.37
3	"	3	193°	760	56.30	56.50	4.46	4.54
4	Benothiazole	1	248°	544	47.18	47.20	3.70	3.75
5	"	2	194°	640	49.20	49.60	3.82	3.95
6	"	3	249°(d)	740	51.20	51.60	4.00	4.12
7	Quinoline-4	1	197°	615	52.70	52.80	4.10	4.20
8	"	2	211°	711	54.48	54.70	4.50	4.37
9	Benoxazole	1	180°	505	48.80	48.99	3.60	3.88
10	Pyridine-2	1	197°	538	48.00	48.00	4.00	4.22
11	"	2	211°	630	50.40	50.40	4.30	4.41

*Vide structure (I).

FIG. 3

TABLE II

*Unsymmetrical cyanines derived from 4-p-bromophenylthiazole.**

Dye No.	Nature of nucleus B.	Value of n .	M.P.	λ max.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Benzothiazole	1	215°	554 m μ	44.80	45.30	3.21	3.16
2	"	2	234°	652	46.30	46.40	3.40	3.36
3	"	3	202°	758	48.50	48.40	3.50	3.54
4	Quinoline-2	1	218°	590	48.70	48.97	3.50	3.55
5	"	2	223°	690	50.83	50.98	3.68	3.74
6	"	3	161°	785	52.60	52.70	3.90	3.90

* Vide structure (II).

General Methods.—In order to prepare the dyes, recorded in Tables I and II, the desired 2-acetanilido derivatives (1 *M*) and the methiodides of the heterocyclic compounds with the reactive methyl group in 2-position (1 *M*) were dissolved in pyridine or absolute ethanol and to it triethylamine (1 *M*) was added and the reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for 10 to 20 minutes. Excess of solvent was then removed by distillation at reduced pressure. In most of the cases, a gummy product was left behind on removal of the solvent. It was washed with a little water and crystallised from methanol. In those cases where the gummy product did not crystallise, the gum was dissolved in methanol and the dye was precipitated by addition of ether. The process was repeated two or three times and the dye was finally crystallised from methanol.

Bis-(4-p-bromophenylthiazole-3-methyl)-2,2'-trimethincyanine Iodide.—4-*p*-Br c n o-phenyl-2,3-dimethylthiazolium iodide (0.4 g.) and triethylorthoformate (0.2 g.) were boiled in dry pyridine for 30 minutes. The desired product separated after removal of pyridine under reduced pressure. It was washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 240°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 40.83; H, 2.71. C₂₃H₂₁N₂Br₂IS₂ requires C, 40.95; H, 2.82%).

Bis-(4-p-bromophenylthiazole-3-methyl)-2,2'-pentamethincyanine Iodide.—4-*p*-Br c n c-phenyl-2,3-dimethylthiazolium iodide (0.4 g.) and trimethoxypropene (0.1 g.) were boiled in pyridine (10 ml) for 15 minutes. The product separating on addition of ether was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 215°, yield 48%. (Found: C, 42.78; H, 3.14. C₂₅H₂₃N₂Br₂IS₂ requires C, 43.0; H, 3.0%).

Bis-(4-p-bromophenylthiazole-3-methyl)-2,2'-heptamethincyanine Iodide.—4-*p*-Bromo-phenyl-2-(2-acetanilido-1,3,5-hexatrienyl)-3-methylthiazolium iodide (0.5 g.) and 4-*p*-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (0.39 g.) were refluxed in pyridine (10 ml) for 30 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled and removal of pyridine at reduced pressure left a gummy product, which was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 260° (decomp.), yield 42%. (Found: C, 49.7; H, 3.7. C₂₇H₂₃N₂Br₂IS₂ requires C, 50.0; H, 3.8%).

Bis-(5-phenylamino-3-methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole)-trimethincyanine Iodide.—5-Phenyl-amino-2,3-dimethylthiadiazolium iodide (0.6 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.2 g.) in dry pyridine (10 ml) were refluxed for 30 minutes. The dye was precipitated by addition of ether to the reaction mixture. It was crystallised from methanol, m. p. 218°, yield 52%. (Found: C, 44.2; H, 3.88. C₂₀H₂₁N₅IS₂ requires C, 44.47; H, 3.9%). This shows absorption maximum at 542 m μ .

Bis-(5-phenylamino-3-methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole)-pentamethincyanine Iodide.—5-Phenylamino-2,3-dimethylthiadiazolium iodide (0.6 g.) and trimethoxypropene (0.3 g.) were refluxed in pyridine (10 ml) for 30 minutes. A deep blue solution was obtained which showed absorption peak at 638 m μ . Attempts to get the solid product did not meet with success.

TABLE III

Serial No.	Abs. max. of the sym. trimethincyanine derived from the		Mean.	Observed abs. max. of the unsym. cyanine (Ref. Table II).	Deviation.
	Fixed basic nucleus (thiadiazole).	Second basic nucleus (indicated).			
1	542 m μ	610 m μ (Quinoline-2)	567 m μ	567 m μ	9 m μ
2	542	660 (Benzothiazole)	551	544	7
3	542	710 (Quinoline-4)	626	515	11
4	542	560 (Pyridine-2)	551	538	13
5	542	480 (Benzoxazole)	511	505	6

TABLE IV

Serial No	Abs. maximum of symmetrical pentamethincyanine derived from the		Mean	Obs. abs. max. of the unsym. cyanine (Ref. Table II).	Deviation.
	Fixed basic nucleus (thiadiazole).	Second basic nucleus (nature of the nucleus indicated).			
6	638 m μ	710 m μ (Quinoline-2)	674 m μ	662 m μ	12 m μ
7	638	660 (Benzothiazole)	649	640	9
8	638	810 (Quinoline-4)	724	711	13
9	638	660 (Pyridine-2)	649	630	19

TABLE V

Serial No.	Abs. maximum of the symmetrical heptamethincyanine derived from the		Mean.	Observed abs. maximum of the unsymmetrical cyanine (Ref. Table II).	Deviation.
	Fixed basic nucleus (thiadiazole).	Second basic nucleus (nature of nucleus indicated).			
10	748 m μ	810 m μ (Quinoline-2)	774 m μ	760 m μ	14 m μ
11	738	760 (Benzothiazole)	749	740	9

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